

POLICY BRIEF ON

excellent science communication for society at large through informal activities

Version 2.0

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1 Introduction

The COALESCE project¹ aims to create a sustainable European Competence Centre for Science Communication as the main reference platform for science communication daily practice. The project's objective is to reduce the gap in European societies regarding scientific understanding and tackle concerns about public mistrust and policy responses during crises. This goal is pursued by enhancing the current levels of excellence in science communication, public engagement with science, and co-creation practices. By collaborating with key stakeholders, COALESCE is reshaping the knowledge gained from eight sister projects (CONCISE, RETHINK, QUEST, NEWSERA, TRESKA, ParCos, ENJOI, and GlobalSCAPE) funded through the Science with and for Society (SwafS-19) programme and other past and ongoing EU-funded and national science communication initiatives into resources and tools that promote high-quality, evidence-based, and interdisciplinary science communication.

Europe has a broad community of organisations working outside of the formal education system that contribute to engage and educate diverse audiences in a wide range of scientific topics, including science museums, science centres, science festivals, science outreach organisations and private companies active in science communication. For the purposes of this document, we refer to these as "informal science engagement organisations." These organisations are active in a wide variety of science engagement activities, such as science communication, science learning, or science participation. Throughout this document, we will use the

term "informal science engagement activities" to refer to all such actions.

To support this community in such informal science engagement activities, policy must be in place to address the challenges faced by these organisations. The eight projects that feed into COALESCE made a series of recommendations on how policy can support this work. This policy brief draws together the main conclusions from those projects that pertain to the role of informal science engagement organisations, as well as drawing on the outcomes of a series of COALESCE case clinics carried out with representatives of different organisations, on the topics of climate change, oceans, water and soils, and artificial intelligence and digital transformation, as key topics addressed within COALESCE.

The outcome is a living document with a set of recommendations that evolves across the series of policy briefs as it integrates the outcomes of COALESCE case clinics on each of the four topics aforementioned. While the case clinics inform the challenges that are raised in the Evidence and main findings section of each of the policy briefs and provide key input for the policy recommendations, these are intended to be overarching

2 Evidence and main findings

The eight EU projects that feed into COALESCE identified a number of challenges faced by informal science engagement organisations. The COALESCE project also runs a series of case clinic activities that feed into these challenges identified below. For this policy brief, three clinics were conducted, focusing on public engagement (PE) on the topics of climate change; oceans, water and soils; and artificial intelligence. The outcomes of the clinics held so far are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Challenges and policy-based solutions identified by PE practitioners during the COALESCE clinics.

<p>CLIMATE</p> <p>Practitioners point out challenges related to (1) finding the right balance between communicating information about climate change and opening up dialogue with audiences, taking into account their emotions and perspectives, and (2) overcoming the sense of ‘hopelessness’ of audiences when facing issues of such a global and systemic nature as climate change.</p> <p>To support engagement on climate change, policy should (1) promote dedicated, well-funded science communication departments within research institutions; (2) reform funding structures to support longer-term, community-led, and co-designed climate projects with built-in communication goals; and (3) build capacity through professional training, evaluation literacy, and recognition programmes that incentivize impactful public engagement by researchers.</p>	<p>WATER, OCEANS & SOILS</p> <p>Practitioners highlight key challenges such as (1) struggling to reach diverse audiences due to top-down approaches that overlook community perspectives and needs; (2) a mismatch between how content is communicated and what resonates with people, such as storytelling and emotion over facts; and (3) limitations to inclusive engagement due to structural barriers like time, funding, and lack of support for reflection and evaluation.</p> <p>Policy support should prioritize equitable science communication by (1) funding pre-engagement phases, especially in underserved and non-English-speaking regions; (2) promote the inclusion of storytelling and audience-centred approaches in public engagement training for researchers; and (3) formally recognize and support public engagement as a core role within institutions.</p>
<p>AI & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION</p> <p>Practitioners identify challenges in (1) keeping up to date with the fast-paced developments both in the technical and ethical aspects of AI; (2) striking a balance between the different public engagement needs around the topic of AI, e.g. informing people on how to use AI, and engaging on the ethical considerations around its use; (3) navigating the vast scope of</p>	<p>HEALTH & VACCINES</p> <p>N/A</p>

information about AI technologies, especially amidst the perceived lack of transparency by AI developers and the perceived lack of digital literacy amongst AI users.

Practitioners recommend that **policy supports** engagement on AI by (1) creating dedicated funding for community-led and experimental work; (2) embedding co-design with diverse communities into policymaking; and (3) promoting open access to publicly funded AI research and data to foster transparency and equity.

The case clinic outcomes were later analysed in conjunction with the challenges identified in the eight projects, resulting in the evidence and main findings hereby described. These challenges are summarised as follows:

1. Informal science engagement activities are not inclusive enough and do not engage a broader range of audiences

The current landscape of mainstream informal science engagement activities reflects a dominance of white, Western perspectives, leading to a lack of diversity and inclusion. This narrow viewpoint limits the effectiveness and relevance of such practices globally. Museums, for instance, primarily engage economically privileged and ethnic majority audiences, overlooking underrepresented groups. These underrepresented groups are varied and differ depending on cultural contexts, but can include factors such as ethnicity, culture, economic background, sex, gender, sexual orientation, religion, age, education and ability.

To address this, there is a need for informal science engagement activities to adapt and become more socially inclusive. This entails reevaluating existing approaches, broadening topics of interest, and actively involving diverse voices. One current challenge is the importance of representation in museums, advocating for exhibitions that address societal inequalities and hiring staff from diverse backgrounds, in positions where people from those backgrounds are underrepresented. Additionally, special relevance should be given to making complex technological topics accessible to diverse audiences at an audience-appropriate level, as for example communication and

information about AI may exclude certain demographics with lower digital literacy.

Moreover, informal activities should move beyond one-way dissemination and prioritise engaging with audiences on a deeper level, considering their personal contexts, beliefs, and trust. Achieving this requires concerted efforts from institutions to set clear inclusion standards and allocate resources accordingly. One particular challenge to take into account, is the risk of informal science engagement activities being tokenistic or extractive, where there is an insufficient investment of time and resources expended into ensuring a solid alignment between the activities' objectives and the needs and expectations of the target audiences. The field should make strides to more strongly address the audience's needs beyond their learning goals to more strongly account for this risk. To this end, participants highlighted the potential of co-producing communication products and informal activities with the target communities.

2. Informal science engagement activities struggle to balance education with dialogue

The evolving trend in informal science engagement activities involves fostering direct contact between the public and researchers through enquiry-based approaches and dialogue formats. This participatory approach aligns with the role of informal science engagement organisations. However, there is a tension between maintaining engagement and fulfilling the educational role of these organisations, highlighting the importance of striking a balance.

Challenges arise in framing science appropriately, avoiding shallow communication and ensuring inclusivity. Practitioners often fail to take a participatory approach: understanding and valuing the prior knowledge, values, cultural contexts and interests of audiences and involving them in co-design of their informal activities; and engaging them as active participants in the dialogue fostered during these activities.

Collaboration between formal and informal learning institutions is advocated to maximise impact. Pedagogy plays a key role in designing engaging activities and there is a need for synergy between education and public engagement efforts. Enhancing these connections can optimise resources and amplify the impact of informal science engagement initiatives. Activities should also focus on creating safe spaces for dialogue, questioning and exploration. Practitioners in the clinics strongly expressed the need for formats where participants can express concerns and emotions about science and technology topics without fear of judgment, allowing for more meaningful dialogue about complex topics.

3. Science communication practitioners lack skills and training

There is a critical need for training of informal science engagement professionals to address the challenges they face. These professionals have very different training needs to scientists who communicate their research. A broad range of practitioners emphasise the necessity for dedicated training, especially concerning the creation and design of engagement activities and materials.

Moreover, practitioners stressed the importance of innovative content development programs that bring together various professionals, including communicators, AI-specialised researchers, artists, educators, social scientists and designers. This interdisciplinary approach is seen as vital for the evolution of new science engagement formats. Practitioners further identified the need for standardised and specialised training to develop a greater understanding of the functioning and ethical implications of emerging technologies, such as AI.

However, the diverse contexts of informal science engagement activities pose challenges in establishing universal quality criteria, contributing to variations in academic programs and professional training. Recognising this complexity is crucial for enhancing the skills and capabilities of practitioners to effectively engage with diverse audiences and address the evolving needs of the field.

4. Audiences do not always trust the science with which they are engaging

The level of trust in scientific information varies among different demographics and regions, reflecting a complex interplay of factors. Citizens tend to place greater trust in information originating from scientists and public figures, associating trust with transparency and independence in funding and ideology. Informal science engagement organisations such as museums, associations and libraries, which are linked to the local context, can also play a key role in generating trust and communicating uncertainty.

However, there exists a sense of ambivalence among audiences regarding the quantity and quality of science information available to them. Despite abundant media coverage, audiences feel that scientific issues are often presented superficially and in a sensationalised way, contributing to doubts about accuracy and bias: evidence points to examples such as the debates around the climate crisis and artificial intelligence.

Moreover, structural barriers within the scientific landscape can further undermine public trust. Limited collaboration across disciplines, restricted access to research findings, and communication practices that exclude non-expert audiences can contribute to a perceived disconnect between science and society. Addressing these issues requires a sustained investment in inclusive, transparent, and participatory approaches to informal science engagement, thereby supporting openness, integrity, and knowledge sharing between the scientific community and societal actors.

Furthermore, practitioners indicated that trust issues are particularly acute with emerging technologies, such as AI, where hype and misinformation often create unrealistic expectations or fears. Ethical concerns about AI raise important questions that science engagement practitioners must address, including issues of bias, privacy, security, and decision-making authority. The rapid pace of AI development presents additional challenges, as information quickly becomes outdated.

5. Audiences experience a sense of hopelessness regarding key societal challenges

Europeans often experience anxiety and a sense of hopelessness when engaging in dialogue about key societal challenges, particularly the climate crisis. The urgency and complexity of the issue, coupled with the magnitude of its potential impacts, contribute to feelings of apprehension and despair among individuals.

People are increasingly concerned about the consequences of climate change, ranging from extreme weather events to biodiversity loss and resource depletion. Moreover, the perceived lack of effective action at both national and international levels exacerbates feelings of helplessness and frustration.

The intricate interplay between environmental, social, and economic factors further complicates the dialogue, leading to feelings of uncertainty and overwhelm. An emphasis on individual responsibility is sometimes perceived as contributing to the problem, with many Europeans struggling to reconcile the scale of the challenge with their individual ability to effect meaningful change.

6. There is a need for specific frameworks concerning emerging and disruptive technologies

The existing debates around AI reinforce this issue, with practitioners noting the rapid emergence of numerous challenges of widely differing natures related to the technology. In addition, the lack of public deliberation around AI topics may once again leave audiences feeling that they lack input and agency over the way in which this technology is shaped. In

both cases, the disconnect between awareness and action can perpetuate feelings of powerlessness and disengagement, hindering constructive dialogue and collective action.

3 Policy recommendations

1. Ensure informal science engagement activities are inclusive and equitable

- The future of informal science engagement must prioritise building activities with marginalised voices, rather than for marginalised groups. Achieving this involves collaborating globally to understand diverse community needs and integrating them into research and communication activities.
- Marginalised communities should be involved in the co-creation of activities through working with associations, communities and schools. Informal science engagement organisations play a crucial role in promoting equity and accessibility.
- Support systems should be established by governing bodies, associations, and funding agencies to aid these organisations in becoming more socially inclusive spaces. This support could include allocating funds based on staff training in diversity and inclusion, organising activities on socially relevant topics, and implementing inclusive organisational structures.
- Encouraging organisations to develop publicly available social inclusion policies, hiring diverse personnel and promoting diversity, equity, and inclusion working groups are also essential steps. The focus should be long-term actions that recognise and value the knowledge, experiences, interests, and identities of diverse audiences.
- Funding and evaluation should be prioritised based on the diversity of participants and their impact, rather than solely quantitative measures. Informal science engagement activities should be supported by the development of ethical frameworks that encourage transparency and equity. This is particularly important for engagement on emerging technologies like AI that have far-reaching societal implications.

2. Promote dialogue in informal science engagement

- Funders and governance bodies must embrace dialogic approaches, fostering collaboration and experimentation beyond traditional methods, including the co-production of community-centred engagement activities.
- Informal science engagement should be acknowledged for its pivotal role in people's learning experiences, science literacy enhancement, fostering the enjoyment and motivation to learn about science, acquiring new skills, creating opportunities to participate in scientific activities, and bridging the gap between science and society.
- Partnerships are encouraged among universities, schools, and informal science engagement organisations to create inclusive engagement frameworks aligned with their shared learning objectives. Additionally, research institutions and knowledge valorisation organisations are advised to utilise partnerships with informal science engagement organisations to elevate public engagement within their institutional strategies.
- Adopting dialogue approaches and strengthening informal science engagement can foster a more inclusive environment, with an impact for participants but also for the systems behind research and policy. This collaborative effort between informal and formal educational institutions, and research organisations contributes to building a more engaging and accessible science engagement landscape beneficial for all. Creating safe spaces and formats for critical discussions about science and technology topics can allow for open conversations about both audiences' concerns, emotions and expectations. This can lead to a better understanding of audiences' needs regarding topics such as climate change and AI.

3. Support training for informal science engagement practitioners

- Dedicated training and upskilling programmes should be organised by funders, governance bodies and associations in collaboration with academia.
- Training and upskilling sessions should cover essential skills for innovative techniques of participation, co-creation and dialogue: how to analyse and engage audiences, how to involve the public in co-design of activities, or how to foster cooperation among a wide range of stakeholder profiles, for example. They should also include the production of engaging materials, innovative content development, and fostering diversity, equality, and inclusion; as well as addressing knowledge gaps such as those related to social sciences and strategic communication.

- Specialized training programs that combine technical knowledge with ethical considerations is key for informal science engagement around topics of emerging technologies, such as AI. Practitioners should be supported in understanding and communicating both the capabilities of such technologies as well as their potential societal implications.
- Educational curricula from schools and universities should support informal science engagement activities in raising literacy around tech and digital topics such as AI.
- Knowledge sharing should be facilitated among practitioners through workshops, sustainable training opportunities, journal clubs, mentoring, shadowing and networking initiatives is crucial for empowering practitioners and enhancing the quality of science communication efforts. The inclusion of researchers, ethics experts and social scientists can further strengthen these knowledge sharing mechanisms, particularly when it pertains to knowledge about emerging technologies and their societal implications.

4. Foster a multi-stakeholder approach to informal science engagement

- The involvement of a broad set of stakeholders in science engagement is crucial. There should be support for informal science engagement organisations to work with a diverse set of organisations: researchers, industry, civil society organisations, policymakers and public institutions, but also artists and other cultural stakeholders.
- In addition, local and specialised communities of knowledge holders should be involved in co-producing science communication products and strategies geared towards explaining complex environmental interconnections
- Informal science engagement activities around emerging technologies with important societal consequences would further benefit from bringing together technological experts with ethicists, social scientists, and communication specialists to develop more holistic approaches to engaging in such technologies.
- National and regional support should be fostered for this by establishing local, national, and international hubs. These hubs would serve as knowledge brokers between informal science engagement community members, scientists, policymakers, and other stakeholders.
- Hubs should facilitate knowledge sharing, collaboration, and dialogue, with the aim of bridging gaps between different groups. Local centres would ensure relevance in their activities and connect with resources. At national level, centres would provide support, mentorship, and lobby for change. Larger international centres would facilitate global collaborations and ensure the innovation and inclusivity of informal science engagement efforts worldwide.

5. Integrate reflective practice into informal science engagement

- Reflective practice must be supported within science engagement practice at all levels: from policy agendas, through funding organisations and at institutional level. It should not be solely the responsibility of individuals but embraced by organisations and institutions to foster deeper engagement with audiences and improve science–society interactions.
- Collaborative reflective practice sessions should be integrated, enabling participants to challenge assumptions and gain new insights into their communication practices. This practice should also ensure practitioners value emotions alongside opinions and see that engagement on the topic can be as valuable as convincing audiences of the science. The AI case clinic highlighted the importance of reflecting on how communication about AI technologies might reinforce existing power structures or biases, recommending that practitioners regularly examine their framing of technological issues and consider whose voices are being prioritized or marginalized.
- These reflective practices should furthermore include considerations of how informal science engagement activities affect and reinforce existing emotional responses and biases in audiences and scientists. Practitioners need spaces and support for regularly examining their framing of science and technology issues and consider which sentiments and biases are being reinforced or neglected.

4 Sustainability and legacy

This policy brief is designed to be dynamic, serving as a living document that will continually evolve throughout the project. It will incorporate insights gleaned from COALESCE case clinics focusing on four key topics: Climate; Water, oceans and soils; Artificial Intelligence and Digital Transformation; and Health. So far, three case clinics covering the first three topics have been conducted and their outcomes inform this current version. As each case clinic explores real-world scenarios and examines challenges within these thematic areas, the document will evolve with the findings and recommendations generated. The outcomes will also feed additional capacity building, communication and advocacy activities.

5 Methodology

This document was developed following a thorough review of the outcomes of the eight projects that feed into COALESCE (CONCISE, RETHINK, QUEST, NEWSERA, TRESCA, ParCos, ENJOI, and GlobalSCAPE) with a particular focus on their findings and recommendations that pertain to the role of informal science engagement organisations. These were analysed and merged according to the commonalities between the different projects outcomes.

Additionally, three case clinics were organised within COALESCE that brought together around 80 practitioners in informal science engagement from a range of profiles (including freelancers, museum professionals and outreach workers) backgrounds (research profiles, communications professionals and people with a cultural management or heritage background), and countries (from across Europe and beyond), recruited from the COALESCE Community of Practice. These clinics engaged the participants around specific challenges in informal science engagement on the topics of climate

change; oceans, water and soils; and artificial intelligence and digital transformation.

Each clinic followed a carefully facilitated series of steps: following a warm-up, there was a brainstorm and prioritisation activity to select a challenge, followed by a round of questions from participants on the selected challenge, and a subsequent round of recommendations. Finally there was a round of reflection and take-home messages from the group. The selected challenges and take-home messages gathered during the clinics were incorporated into the findings and recommendations in this policy brief.

To further reinforce the relevance and applicability of the recommendations, the brief was reviewed in light of current European policy developments, in particular the findings of the MLE *on Public Engagement in Research and Innovation*. This ensured alignment with broader strategic priorities within the European Research Area and allowed framing the recommendations within a wider policy context.

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7 Project details

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PARTNERS

WEBSITE <https://coalesceproject.eu>

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